

4QPseudo Ezekiel

also known as “4QWords of Ezekiel”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Jewish Traditions, Late Second Temple Judaism, Text, Apocalyptic Literature, Early Jewish Literature, Dead Sea Scrolls

Words of Ezekiel (WoEzek) or Pseudo-Ezekiel are the designated names to a group of manuscripts found among the Dead Sea Scrolls. The composition which was not known prior to its discovery in Qumran is commonly associated with the prophet Ezekiel and his oracles. WoEzek was preserved in at least three fragmentary parchment copies, sharing an overlapping textual section: 4Q385, 4Q386 and 4Q388. Two additional sigla numbers are associated with the composition: 4Q385b which contains a single fragment, and the papyrus scroll 4Q391. These manuscripts do not share any textual parallels with the scrolls stated above, yet 4Q385b and 4Q391 are identified as additional copies of WoEzek based on their rewriting style of the scriptural text of Ezekiel. The earliest manuscript, 4Q391 is dated to 150-100 BCE, while the other scrolls are roughly dated to 50-25 BCE. Although the composition was found in Qumran, its content does not show any special connection to the religious movement settled at the site (the Yahad), and thus it could have originated among different social groups in the Second Temple period. The composition contains a series of visions revealed to the prophet Ezekiel. Some of the preserved oracles also appear in the biblical (or the scriptural) versions of the Book of Ezekiel known today, such as the vision of the dry bones (Ezek 37) or the merkavah (chariot) vision (Ezek 1 and 10). Other sections are not known from any textual witnesses of scriptural Ezekiel, and their context is rather the Jewish literary and ideological framework in the Second Temple period. WoEzek is often categorised as “pseudo-prophetic” text (Dimant, 2001), and “rewritten scripture” (Zahn, 2014). It means that the composition uses the voice of the prophet and rewrites the scriptural source by setting it in a new framework and putting it to a different use. While the fragmentary state of the composition makes it difficult to determine its context, the principal orientation of the text is most likely apocalyptic, as it often highlights the apocalyptic connotation which can be attributed to Ezekiel’s oracles. The text contains references to the “day of the lord” and suggests that the redemption reflected through the vision of the dry bones is promised exclusively to the righteous among Israel, whose reward will be an actual resurrection at the eschatological end of the current universe.

Date Range: 150 BCE - 25 BCE

Region: Jerusalem and Qumran

Region tags: Israel, Qumran, Judean Desert, Jerusalem

The Jewish settlement in Jerusalem and Qumran at the Second Temple period.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Dimant, Devorah. Qumran Cave 4. Volume 21: Parabiblical Texts. Part 4: Pseudo-prophetic Texts. DJD 30. Oxford: Clarendon, 2001.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/search#q='pseudo-ezekiel'>

– Source 1 Description: Digital images of the copies of 4QPseudo Ezekiel in the IAA website

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://sqe.deadseascrolls.org.il/>

– Source 1 Description: The Scripta Qumranica Electronica website is providing online transcriptions of the fragments alongside their images

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment and papyrus.

Notes: 4Q385, 4Q386, 4Q388 and 4Q385b are written on parchment, while 4Q391 is inscribed on papyrus.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Some corrections and a single literary variants are present among the copies of the composition

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– Yes

Notes: The copies of the composition were found in Cave 4, close to the settlement in Qumran.

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: The different copies of the composition were found in Cave 4 in Qumran.

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– I don't know

↳ Domestic contexts

– I don't know

Notes: Although the text was found in Cave 4, the Qumran site had a local settlement.

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cave 4 in Qumran often referred to as "the library", due to the amount of manuscripts found in this cave.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: We do not know whether the scrolls that were found in the Qumran site were also produced there, or brought from elsewhere. However, the papyrus copy of WoEzek, 4Q391, has several distinctive features such as its calligraphy, orthography and the writing of the divine name in four dots. These features together led scholars to suggest that this copy is originated in a "private collection" or some sort, or meant to be stored in a private library. (Smith, 1995).

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: While Word of Ezekiel is not part of the Jewish canon, it is based on the scriptural text of Ezekiel.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text is written in Classical Hebrew, however, it contains several Aramaic phrases, as well as unique words (hapax legomenon).

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The composition addresses the nation of Israel in general.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is hard to define the context of the composition, the text reflects some eschatological expectations.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: 4Q391 is dated to 150-125 BCE, while the other copies are dated to 50-25 BCE.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The overlapping section in 4Q385 and 4Q386 contains slightly different text. 4Q386 repeats the process of the restoration of the bones (ויעלו עליהם גדים).

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: The evidence from Qumran are characterized with an extensive amount of textual fluidity. The textual fluidity, however, does not influence the authoritative status of different copies of compositions.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Jewish Canon, or the "Bible", did not yet exist in the Second Temple period. While the text associated today with the Jewish Canon enjoyed authoritative status, other compositions could be possibly viewed as equally authoritative. For the case of the Book of Ezekiel and WoEzek see Popović (2010).

Reference: Schuller, Eileen. *The Dead Sea Scrolls and Canon and Canonization*, n.d..

Reference: Popović, Mladen. "Prophet, Books and Texts: Ezekiel, Pseudo-ezekiel and the Authoritativeness of Ezekiel Traditions in Early Judaism". In *Authoritative Scriptures in Ancient Judaism*, n.d..

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text contains some rewritten versions of oracles known from the Book of Ezekiel.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The text was preserved only among the scrolls that were found in Qumran, Cave 4. However, scholars suggest that it is not implausible that the authors of other composition were familiar with Words of Ezekiel. Bauckman (1992) for example, recognizes resemblances between WoEzek and the Apocalypse of Peter. Similarly, Kister (1990) points out similar ideas in WoEzek and the Epistle of Barnabas

Reference: Kister, Menahem. "Barnabas and Second Ezekiel". *Revue Biblique*, n.d..

Reference: Bauckman, Richard. "A Quotation from 4Q Second Ezekiel in the Apocalypse of Peter". *Revue De Qumran*, n.d..

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text frames the Ezekielian vision of the dry bones in an eschatological framework. The vision is the response to Ezekiel's query regarding the fate of the righteous among Israel ("I have seen many among (the people of) Israel who loved your name and walked in your wa[ys. And the]se (things), when they will b[e] and how their acts of faithfulness will be repaid" 4Q385 2 2-3). This context suggests that the prophecy in WoEzek claims that will be some kind of physical restoration of the spirits of the righteous.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text is too fragmentary, and any additional details are not preserved.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The question remains in which kind of temporality the righteous among Israel are resurrected.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: The Pharisees, who associated the most with modern Judaism, movement associated with the Qumran site believed in afterlife.

- ↳ What are the historically minority positions?
 - Specify: The Sadducees rejected the belief in afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high-god is present
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity
 - I don't know
 - Notes: While God's residence is indeed the heavens, the divine merkavah 4Q385 6) suggests that he can move around.

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: While the Book of Ezekiel itself selected to David's dynasty as selected by the Lord, WoEzek does not preserve any references.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– I don't know

Notes: Ezek 20:25 describes that God gave Israel "laws that were not good".

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: While neither WoEzek nor the Book of Ezekiel specify further details, the character of the God of Israel is universal and almighty.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

Notes: Ezek 8:12 states "O mortal, have you seen what the elders of the House of Israel are doing in the darkness, everyone in his image-covered chamber? For they say, 'The LORD does not see us; the Lord has abandoned the country.'" (JPS translation). The verse suggests that God aware of the deeds of the elders.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

Notes: God delivers to Ezekiel the sights regarding the future of the nation, as well as notifies him regarding personal events, such as the death of his wife.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

Notes: See 4Q385 2 2-3. Ezekiel asks regarding the "reward" of the righteous for their deeds.

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Ezekiel directly asks God "in place of my sorrow, gladden my soul" (4Q385 4 1-2)

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: God directly communicates with the prophet Ezekiel.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars suggest that the description of Ezekiel's symbolic acts in chapter 4 for example, where he lies down on his side in order to reflect on his oracles, may symbolize some ecstatic state.

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Yes
Notes: Prophets

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The vision of the dry bones and the resurrection in the current composition can be understood together with the presence of the spirits of the dead righteous among Israel.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– Yes

Notes: As far as we know, the beings can be seen only by the prophet. (see the Merkavah vision in 4Q385 6).

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 4Q391 fragment 52 mentions the "angel of God". However, the text is only partially preserved, and it is unknown whether Ezekiel communicates with the angel.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The beings are carrying the divine Merkavah, supposedly from and back to the Jerusalemite temple.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: While the Merkavah vision as it is attested in WoEzek (4Q385 6) rather reflects the description of Ezek 1, the Merkavah in Ezek 11 suggest an expanded angelological view. See Halperin, *The Faces of the Chariot*.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: Ezek 11 potentially describes several rows of angels carrying the chariot, arranged by hierarchical order.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: at least by Ezekiel himself.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: WoEzek mentions attests only the beings carrying the Merkavah (4Q385 6), and the "angel of God" (4Q391 52).

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text encourages observing the Mosaic law in order to be recompensated at the eschaton. The criteria of the desired behaviour is thus the laws given in the Torah.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The vision of the temple itself is present in WoEzek (4Q391 65). While it is possible to assume that the temple vision will be related to the offerings in the temple, no further details are preserved.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 4Q385b, for example, describes that "Egypt will be pierced by the sword" (4Q385b 3). 4Q388 6 also has a warfare context while derives from Ezek 39, however, the preserved text is too partial to suggest any further conclusions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No material related to the matter was preserved.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: 4Q385 2 3 and 4Q391 36 rather mention the "covenant" made between Israel and God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: The Torah commends to respect the elders (Lev 19:32)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Notes: Lev 19:16

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: In Ezekiel only with reference to the priests (Ezek 44). See also for example Lev 9:1-15.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The note is relevant to the entire section. 4Q385b contains a prophecy against

Egypt and other, geographically close nations. The text derived by the third oracle upon Egypt in Ezek 30:1-19. The prophecy describes the event as יום אבדן גוים ("the day of doom of the nations" 4Q385b line 2). It is however not indicated whether the punishment is meted by God himself, or through war with other nations, and to which extent God is involved in the events.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not unplausible that the text indicated the reason for the punishment of the foreign nations, similar to the Book of Ezekiel itself, however, the text is only partially preserved.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No
Notes: Not with regard to the foreign nations.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Field doesn't know
Notes: See note above discussing the "the day of doom of the nations".

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
– Yes

Notes: The text describes the rightfulness of the righteous: "I have seen many among (the people of) Israel who loved your name and walked in your wa[ys]." (4Q385 2 2-3). Ezekiel thus asks God directly: "how their (-of the righteous-) acts of faithfulness will be repaid?" (4Q385 2 3)

↳ Done only by high god
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The social context of the composition is unknown.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: The reward is promised only to "those who loved your name".

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The note is relevant for the entire section. The promised reward to the righteous is some kind of resurrection, likely even physical. The space that the righteous will be placed after the resurrection and their form are not indicated.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Among the preserved material, no references to messianic beliefs are present.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the text refers several times to the temporality of the events, mainly by using the word $\eta\mu\tau$ ("time" e.g. 4Q388 3 ii 3, 4Q388 6 3), it is unclear in which lifetime the eschaton meant to be. It is rather plausible to assume that the author intended to suggest that the eschaton will happen in his own lifetime, and not this of the prophet Ezekiel, for example.

↳ At specified time in future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future
– Yes

Notes: The composition highlights the urgency of the upcoming eschaton, describing that the time is accelerating in order to realize the upcoming eschaton faster: "And the days will hasten quickly, that the men will say: Are not rushing the days, for the children of Israel will inherit?" (4Q385 4 2-3)

↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: The text promises resurrection only to the righteous among Israel. Therefore, there must be an act of divine judgment.

↳ Restoration of the world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify the fate of the world itself. It is not unplausible that the resurrection will accrue in another space.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While WoEzek itself does not indicate that a new temporal cycle is established, 1 En 80:2, which contains a similar temporal setting ("And in the days of the sinners the years shall be shortened...") indeed suggest that a new cycle starts after the eschaton. For further discussion see Henze (2018).

Reference: Henze, Matthias. "Dimensions of Time in Jewish Apocalyptic Thought: The Case of 4 Ezra". In *Figures of Ezra*, n.d..

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Field doesn't know

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– Field doesn't know

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unknown whether all the humanity will be destroyed at the eschaton and only the righteous will be resurrected later, or some will survive the event.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: Such distinction is not present in the current text.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text encourages "righteous" by ancient Jewish standards. That is to say that the readers are encouraged to follow the Law of the Torah. The request does not specify further details.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Field doesn't know

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Field doesn't know

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Field doesn't know

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Specifically to the covenant made with God.

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

Notes: Only with respect to keeping the Mosaic law perhaps.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Field doesn't know

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: WoEzek does not preserve any references to food ate by Ezekiel himself or other individuals, as it is stated in the Book of Ezekiel.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Israel are called to keep and to act by the Mosaic law.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the partial preservation of the text, we do not know whether the temple related indicated in the Book of Ezekiel were integrated also in the current text.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Field doesn't know

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Notes: While the provenance of the text is unknown, we may assume that the text was written among a Jewish group which believed in afterlife (unlike the Sadducees, for example).

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: 4Q388 6 resemblances with Ezek 39, which describes the Gog of Magog battle. The remains of the fragment, however, are too inconclusive to determine its context.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Food Production

- Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?
– No

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